

INTERFACIAL CRACK GROWTH IN BIMATERIAL COMPOSITE SPECIMENS

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SUMMARY

The interface between two dissimilar composite materials is characterised by mixed mode cohesive laws, determined from double cantilever beam specimens loaded with uneven bending moments. The cohesive laws are used in a finite element model to predict the strength of larger "medium-size" specimens. The predicted strength values are compared with experimental strength values determined independently.

Keywords: cohesive laws, mixed mode cracking, interfaces, modelling, testing

1. INTRODUCTION

Many advanced composite structures, such as wind turbine rotor blades, consist of various types of composite materials joined by adhesive joints or by co-consolidation. One of the most common failure modes in wind turbine blades is delamination, i.e. cracking along interfaces between dissimilar materials, often accompanied by fibre bridging. Since crack bridging is a large-scale fracture process zone, it should be modelled by non-linear fracture mechanics, e.g. by cohesive zone model [1-3].

The purpose of the present study is to investigate the transferability of cohesive laws. More precisely, the aim is to investigate if cohesive laws, determined from double cantilever beam specimens loaded with uneven bending moments (DCB-UBM) [4], can be used for predicting the load required for the propagation of an interface crack between two uneven composite materials in larger medium size specimens, that have a different size, geometry and loading that the DCB specimens.

The study thus includes (i) characterisation of the fracture properties of bimaterial interfaces by fracture mechanics testing, (ii) using the measured fracture properties for the prediction of the load-level that causes delamination cracking in medium-size specimens by numerical simulations, and (iii) validation of the predictions by experimental determination of the strength properties of medium-size specimens.

2. DETERMINATION OF MIXED MODE COHESIVE LAWS

2.1 Theory and experimental procedure

Mixed mode fracture mechanical tests are conducted using a special loading device [4], applying uneven bending moments to bimaterial DCB specimens. A sketch of the test specimen including loads is shown in Fig. 1. The specimen is a mixed mode specimen

and the whole range of mode mixity combinations can be obtained from the same specimen geometry by varying the moment ratio. In the present study, the fracture resistance is measured for eight different nominal mode mixities. The fracture resistance can be calculated from J integral results. The equation for the J integral is identical to the equation for the energy release rate result given by Suo and Hutchinson [5] for small fracture process zone. The J integral result is independent of the crack length and valid for both small-scale fracture process zone and large-scale bridging.

Mixed mode cohesive laws are then obtained from measurement of the fracture resistance and measurements of the end-opening and end-sliding of the fracture process zone, using an approach described elsewhere [6]. Using this method the cohesive law parameters can be directly obtained from the experiments without resorting to iterative processes where a number of finite element calculations are performed until the simulations match the experimental data [7,8].

Figure 1: Sketch of the load and geometry of the DCB-UBM bimaterial specimen loaded with two moments, M_1 and M_2 .

Figure 2. The measured steady-state fracture resistance, J_{ss} , as a function of the nominal mode mixity. Fitting lines for average, upper and lower bounds (used in simulation) are also plotted.

2.2 Results

For all loading conditions, the interface showed increasing fracture resistance, i.e. the crack growth initiated at a certain value of the J integral, denoted J_0 , and with increasing crack extension J increased, eventually attaining a steady state value, J_{ss} . Crack bridging in the form of cross-over bridging was visible. It is believed that the crack bridging was the cause of the increasing fracture resistance.

Figure 3: Sketch of the principle of medium size specimen.

The fracture resistance showed dependence of the nominal mode mixity, ψ - the term "nominal" is used to indicate that the mode mixity is calculated using a linear-elastic approach (Suo and Hutchinson, 1990). The steady-state fracture resistance J_{ss} is shown as a function of the nominal mode mixity in Figure 2. J_{ss} is practically constant for $0^\circ < \psi < 50^\circ$; however for $50^\circ < \psi < 90^\circ$, J_{ss} increases significantly with increasing ψ . The Figure also includes fits for average as well as upper and lower bounds. These are subsequently used in the numerical simulations.

The measurement of the end-openings showed that the critical normal and tangential openings (viz., the openings where J attains a steady-state value, J_{ss} , and thus the cohesive stresses have decreased to zero), were approximately $2.9 \text{ mm} \pm 0.5 \text{ mm}$ for all mode mixities.

Figure 4: Geometry of the finite element model (dimensions in mm).

3. NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF CRACK GROWTH IN MEDIUM SIZE SPECIMENS

The geometry of the medium size specimens is shown schematically in Fig. 3. A continuous central laminate of material #1 has two layers of material #2 bonded at two

major faces. A delamination crack can propagate along the interfaces between the two materials. The strength of medium size specimens subjected to uniaxial tension (Fig. 3), i.e., the stress level at which the interface crack propagates, is predicted from finite element simulations using the mixed mode cohesive laws determined from the DCB-UBM experiments.

3.1. Geometry, finite element mesh and boundary conditions

The finite element method (Abaqus vs 6.8-2) was used to model the crack growth along the interface of the two different composite materials (laminates). To facilitate the analysis of the simulations symmetry conditions were assumed, thus only half of the medium size specimens was modelled. The effect of this assumption will be discussed in subsequent sections. The modelled geometry is shown in Fig. 4, only one thickness for the short beam was modelled ($H = 10$ mm). The boundary conditions prescribed were: $u_2 = 0$ at the symmetry plane ($x_1 = 0$), where u_i is the displacement vector (the subscript refers to the direction of the displacement, where x_i is the coordinate axis). At $x_1 = 1200$ mm, the edge was constrained in the x_1 direction ($u_1 = 0$). The external loading was applied in displacement control, u_1 , at ($x_1 = 0$).

The crack growth at the interface of the two composite laminates was modelled using 4-noded cohesive elements. A finite cohesive element thickness ($h_c = 0.005$ mm) was used to avoid interpenetration of the two laminates. The selected thickness corresponds to 4% of the cohesive element length. The finite element mesh used near the cohesive zone is shown in Fig. 5 (at $x_1 = 440$ mm). It can be seen that for the composite laminates, four-node elements and three-node elements were used. This combination allows for efficient mesh transitions.

Figure 5: Deformed finite element mesh near the end of cohesive zone. The cohesive elements are illustrated by red colour.

3.2. Material properties and cohesive law parameters

The composite laminates were modelled as isotropic, linear elastic solids with $E_1 = 12.60$ GPa for the middle laminate and $E_2 = 11.86$ GPa for the side laminates. For both materials, the Poisson's ratio was set equal to 0.3.

Table 1: Fitting parameters for linear and exponential cohesive laws.

	Mode I		Mode II	
	Peak stress, $\hat{\sigma}_n$ (MPa)	Critical opening, δ_n^o (mm)	Peak stress, $\hat{\sigma}_t$ (MPa)	Critical opening, δ_t^o (mm)
Linear				
Upper bound	0.52	2.5	1.44	2.5
Average fit	0.68	2.5	1.68	2.5
Lower bound	0.80	2.5	2.72	2.5
Exponential				
Upper bound	1.35	2.5	3.70	2.5
Average fit	1.75	2.5	4.35	2.5
Lower bound	2.77	2.5	4.94	2.5

Figure 6: Examples of linear and exponential softening laws for Mode I (data from Table 1).

The cohesive law parameters were approximated from the DCB-UBM experiments described in the previous section. Two idealised cohesive laws were assumed for all mode mixities: linear and exponential softening. The parameters for the idealised cohesive laws are given in Table 1 for Mode I and Mode II. Three (not independent) parameters are needed for the complete description of a linear cohesive law: fracture energy, critical opening and peak stress. Since the steady state fracture energy, J_{ss} , and the critical opening are more accurately measured from the experiments, the peak stresses were adjusted so that area under the stress-separation curve equals J_{ss} for the measured critical openings for the specific mode mixity.

As seen in Table 1, the critical opening is the same for all mode mixities in accordance with the experimental observations presented earlier. As mentioned above, the peak stresses were calculated from the critical openings and the steady state fracture

resistance for Mode I and II. The three different peak stresses (or cohesive laws), for each softening behaviour, correspond to the three different estimations of the J_{ss} as a function of the phase angle: average fit and lower and upper bounds as can be seen in Fig. 2.

In principle, no opening of the cohesive zone should occur before the cohesive element starts to fail. However, in the finite element method an initial rising part is necessary (see Fig. 6). This initial stiffness can be considered as a penalty parameter that should be as high as possible but still not causing numerical problems. In the current work the stiffness in the normal, k_n , and tangential direction, k_t , were set equal to $k_n = k_t \cong 20 E_2 h_c$.

The simulated crack extension is calculated as follows. The stress opening relationship after crack initiation, i.e. for Mode I, is given by:

$$\sigma_n = (1 - D)k_n \delta_n \quad (1)$$

where D is a damage variable that ranges from 0 for undamaged cohesive elements to 1 for complete failure. Since in the experiments the crack opening is visible only after a certain opening, the simulated crack extension is computed based on D values that correspond to an opening $\delta \cong 200 \mu\text{m}$.

3.3. Solution method

It is well-known that implicit solvers encounter convergence problems since the stiffness matrix becomes ill-conditioned as the crack grows and a steady state condition is approached. A number of numerical stabilisation techniques exist to overcome this problem but in general it is difficult to achieve steady-state conditions. Therefore, an explicit solver was used to solve the problem of Fig. 4 under quasi-static conditions. In all cases it was ensured that the kinetic and artificially dissipated energy was less than 1% of the strain energy.

The cohesive zone (see Figs. 4 and 5), with properties listed in Table 1, is prescribed for $440 \text{ mm} < x_1 < 820 \text{ mm}$. For $820 \text{ mm} < x_1 < 840 \text{ mm}$, which coincides with the bimaterial corner, a different cohesive law is used. Since in the experiments this end was clamped with a vice to prevent crack initiation and propagation, the cohesive law in this region should not allow for crack initiation and growth. This is achieved by setting the peak stresses ~ 500 times higher than the peak stresses in Table 1. The cohesive element stiffness was the same as in the first cohesive element zone.

4. MEASUREMENTS OF STRENGTH OF MEDIUM SIZE SPECIMENS

4.1. Test procedures

Medium size specimens (having similar thickness ratio as in the model study) are loaded in uniaxial tension in a universal materials testing machine. Interfacial cracking is determined from measurements of the displacement jump across the interface, from images and acoustic emission data. Finally, the predicted strength values are compared with experimental strength values, and the accuracy of the approach is evaluated.

Bimaterial specimens consisting of a centre laminate with symmetrical side laminates (see Figure 7) were made with a 13 μm thin slip foil (length 80 mm, width 40 mm) between the side laminates and the centre laminate at one end of the side laminates. Since the specimens were made in the laboratory, their properties may differ from the properties of the materials in wind turbine blades. Since preliminary tests showed difficulties in starting the cracks at the slip foil, a 45-50 mm pre-crack was formed manually for both side laminates with a slim steel wedge after clamping the specimen 60 mm from the slip foil using a vice.

Figure 7. Specimens with one laminate in the centre and a (different) side laminate bonded symmetrically to the centre laminate over a part (480 mm) of the length. Two different side laminate thicknesses (5 and 10 mm) were used. (all dimensions in mm).

Figure 8. Photograph of a medium scale specimen during testing; the specimen is mounted in a universal testing machine and subjected to uniaxial tension. The end shown to the left is clamped with a vice; cracking has occurred along the biomaterial interface. The positions of the crack tips are shown by arrows.

A servo-hydraulic testing machine (Instron 8533) with a ± 250 kN load cell (UK084) was operated in displacement control at 1 mm/min to load the specimen in tension. The specimen was clamped with a vice 30 mm from one of the ends without pre-cracks in order to avoid crack growth from that end. Each specimen was equipped with two acoustic emission (AE) sensors to monitor crack development together with two LVDT's (linear variable differential transformer) placed at the slip foil parallel to the

crack to measure the relative displacement of the two layers. In order to ease visual observation of delamination cracks, the side of the specimen was painted white using correction ink, and markers were placed along the interface.

During testing, the load and LVDT signals were recorded with a frequency of 25 Hz on a PC, and the load and AE signals were recorded on a PC dedicated for the AE measurements. Images of the specimen, including data for the elapsed time and the applied load level, were recorded with a few seconds interval by a digital camera (Nikon D200). Fig. 8 shows the set-up of a typical experiment.

Figure 9. Measured force-at-crack-growth as a function of crack extension for two different specimens.

4.2. Experimental results: crack growth in medium size specimens

Fig. 9 shows the experimentally measured data of force as a function of crack length for two different specimens ($H = 10$ mm). There are two different interfaces in each specimen denoted by left and right side in Fig. 9. It can be observed that the crack growth is not symmetric i.e. the crack grows at different rate in the two interfaces. This can be due to different interface properties along the two interfaces (see also Fig. 1 for the variation in interface steady state fracture resistance) or due to asymmetry of the loading occurring as soon as one crack grows more than the other one.

4.3. Comparison of experimental and modelling results

The numerical predictions for the force as a function of crack extension are given in Fig. 10. Results based on different linear cohesive laws (see Table 1) are shown. The experimental data from specimen 2 (left side) are also included (see Fig. 9). The variation of the experimental data is at selected crack extensions are calculated from the rest experimental data of Fig. 9.

Figure 10. Predicted relationship between applied load and crack extension under monotonic loading for various linear cohesive laws (Table 1).

Figure 11. Predicted relationship between applied load and crack extension under monotonic loading for various exponential cohesive laws (Table 1).

As can be seen from Fig. 10, the experimental data lie between the numerical upper and lower bounds. However, for small crack length, the numerical predictions lie below the experimental findings. For long crack extensions, the numerical predictions predict, in general, a higher force for crack extension. For an exponential softening a different trend is observed in Fig 11. Initially the simulations over predict the experimental values as the peak cohesive stress is much higher than in the case of linear softening

(Table 1). As the crack grows the simulations under predict the experiments. Most likely the actual cohesive law lies in between the two idealised cohesive laws used here.

In both the cases: linear and exponential softening laws, the simulations under estimate the fracture resistance as the experimental data lie between the average fit and the upper bound. . Probably this is due to the symmetry conditions used in the model. As can be seen from Fig. 9, the crack at one of the interface usually propagates faster than the other one. This suggests that in the experiments, the interface fracture resistance differs for the two interfaces of the specimen. Using a full model with two different cohesive laws, the predictions would move upwards closer to the experimental data. However, the symmetric model used here, is suitable to demonstrate the prediction of the fracture behaviour of the medium size specimens based on fracture data from small laboratory specimens.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The use of mixed mode cohesive laws, obtained from fracture mechanics testing using the double cantilever beam specimen loaded with uneven bending moments, was demonstrated for strength prediction of medium scale specimens. The predictions were made using idealised linear or exponential softening cohesive laws. A better agreement may be obtained if more precise, non-linear cohesive laws are used.

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